

EFFECT OF NON-ELECTROLYTES ON THE p_H AND SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY OF HYDROGEN CLAY SOLS.*

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Hydrogen clay, as usually obtained from the clay fraction of soil by electro dialysis or repeated leaching with a dilute mineral acid after treatment with 6% hydrogen peroxide to oxidise organic materials contained in it, has characteristic acidic properties (Mitra, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 555; 1940, 10, 317 *et seq.*). The pre-treatment with 6% hydrogen peroxide may not effect a complete removal of the organic matter in all cases. If a hydrogen clay containing some residual organic matter (r.o.m.) is treated with an organic solvent a part of the r.o.m. may be dissolved. Some peculiar observations have been made by us in this connection. It has been found that the addition of traces of alcohol to a hydrogen clay sol produces a sharp rise in the specific conductivity and a correspondingly sharp fall in the p_H (*cf.* Fig. 1). As the concentration of alcohol increases, the conductivity reaches a maximum value and then rapidly decreases and finally tends to remain constant; at the same time, the p_H passes through a minimum value and then increases approaching a constant value towards the end. The maximum conductivity and the minimum p_H are observed at about the same concentration of the added alcohol. On the other hand, control experiments with a hydrochloric acid solution having nearly the same p_H as the sol show that alcohol has practically no effect on the p_H and specific conductivity of the former within the range of concentration (0 to 1.5%) of the alcohol used. The above discontinuous variations in the p_H and specific conductivity of the sol, especially the maximum and minimum, are interesting though it is at present difficult to visualise their real significance. They do not appear to have been previously observed.

The p_H and conductivity of the sol-alcohol mixture change with time. The conductivity tends to increase while the p_H slowly decreases. A slow reaction between the sol and the alcohol is indicated. The curves

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shown below were obtained from measurements made 72 hours after the addition of alcohol to the sol.

The decrease in the conductivity and H^+ -ion concentration of the sol at higher concentrations of the alcohol after an initial increase shows that the alterations in the p_H and conductivity cannot be referred to a simple dissolution of acids from the hydrogen clay by the alcohol, as in that case both the H^+ -ion concentration and the conductivity would go on increasing with increasing concentration of alcohol in the mixture instead of decreasing at the higher concentrations. A hydrogen clay was repeatedly leached with 25% alcohol. It was then washed free from the alcohol and redispersed in water. The p_H and specific conductivity of the redispersed sol showed similar discontinuous variations as the original sol on the addition of small quantities (0 to 2%) of alcohol.

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